

From Seizure or Donation of Antiquities to Their Identification and Research at the British Museum and Repatriation to the Countries of Origin: Recent Case Studies from Afghanistan, Uzbekistan and Iraq

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Abstract

When law enforcement authorities or players in the art market suspect that cultural goods have been acquired illegally, they need experts to determine the quality, origin and value of the objects. In the United Kingdom, the British Museum is the body they turn to in such cases. This article describes the Museum's role in combating antiquities trafficking, shares some of its success stories in returning antiquities to their rightful owners, and shows how the Museum has set an example for others to follow in such cases.

Keywords: The British Museum; Afghanistan; Uzbekistan; Iraq; antiquities trafficking; law enforcement; repatriation

Introduction

The British Museum is the main advisory body in the United Kingdom in the event of any enquiries concerning antiquities, and it works very closely with all law enforcement agencies and market actors, including the UK Border Force, Her Majesty's Revenue and Customs, the National Crime Agency, the Metropolitan Police Service's Art and Antiques Unit, the Arts Council, Art Loss Register, auction houses, dealers, and private collectors.

Our expert advice is sought in confidence. If the items prove to be ancient and in breach of antiquities laws and/or declaration, and the parties concerned consent, we notify the relevant national museum in the country where we believe these objects to have originated, request permission to proceed with the case at hand, and inform their diplomatic representation in London. If we act at the request of a UK law enforcement agency, we then produce an official report, catalogue and photograph the objects. In some cases, if resources permit, we scientifically analyse them in order to answer specific enquiries we may have that help support a case and which may have research value. Our part is then done until we are notified that the objects have been forfeited or disclaimed, and may be returned to the country in question. At that point, we prepare a condition report and a press release, brief interested arts correspondents in the media, work closely with the concerned museum and diplomatic representation to ensure a smooth handover within a schedule which is mutually convenient, and keep relevant government bodies updated. This is a protocol we developed first with our colleagues in the National Museum of Afghanistan in Kabul, and since then with the Ministry of Culture in Uzbekistan and the State Board of Antiquities and Heritage in Baghdad. In each case, the public impact has been huge and very positive, and we plan to unroll this process as a model for other countries in the future.

This article sets out a number of case studies, arranged in chronological order of event by country, and amplifies and updates a previous overview article published by the author (Simpson 2020).

Afghanistan

Sadly, almost every archaeological site in Afghanistan has been damaged by looting, beginning in the late 1960s and still continuing (Simpson 2018: 142). Bronze Age, Hellenistic, Kushan, Buddhist and Islamic antiquities, Buddhist manuscripts and medieval documents have crossed its borders in all directions and flooded the art market for decades. Often these have vague or misleading provenances, as third millennium BC pieces may be labelled Trans-Elamite or Outer Iranian (Amiet 1988), Islamic objects

loosely attributed to Khurasan or treated as art, rather than illegally excavated and trafficked antiquities, and Buddhist or medieval Jewish documents often ascribed to Bamiyan but with little supporting evidence (Bailey 2002; Omland 2006; Pritula 2019).

Eleven years ago, in February 2009, we returned 22 crates to Kabul, which weighed over three tons and contained over 1500 objects seized in Britain between 2003 and 2007 (Simpson 2015a; 2018). The logistics were complex because of the scale of the operation, and we are very grateful to the UK Foreign and Commonwealth Office and the International Red Cross for their generous assistance in physically returning the objects. The returned objects ranged from copper cosmetic flasks, mirrors and weapons looted from 4,000-year-old cemeteries in northern Afghanistan to objects of the Hellenistic, medieval and later periods. Pictures of a selection of the objects were used to illustrate the ICOM Red List of Afghan Antiquities at Risk. Some of the objects were put on display as part of the permanent exhibition galleries in the now-restored National Museum of Afghanistan in Kabul.

In July 2012, in a window of opportunity immediately before the London Olympics, we returned a second very large consignment to Kabul, this time with the generous assistance of the British Armed Forces as we routed them on military flights from Brize Norton to Kabul via Bagram (Fig. 1). This group included some of the famous 'Begram ivories' (Fig. 2) and the so-called 'Fire Buddha', a stunning Gandharan sculpture from Sarai Khwaja, all stolen from the National Museum in Kabul during the civil war but tracked down and purchased on their behalf by John Eskenazi, a respected dealer in Asian art. In such cases, our role is that of a third-party intermediary. These objects were conserved, scientifically analysed, published, and exhibited at the British Museum in 2011 as an additional component to the radically re-interpreted version of the travelling exhibition, *Afghanistan: Crossroads of the Ancient World* (Fig. 3), before being carefully packed for return (Simpson 2011; Passmore *et al.* 2012; Ambers *et al.* 2014; Simpson 2016). The 'Fire Buddha' was placed on display at the National Museum in Kabul (Fig. 4), but has since travelled on loans to Prague and Beijing.

This repatriation consignment also included 821 looted antiquities of similar periods to those seized previously, and amalgamated from five different investigations by the UK Border Force and the Metropolitan Police Service (Simpson 2018). Some were typical Bronze Age cemetery finds, including copper alloy stamp-seals and cosmetic containers (Fig. 5), and chlorite vessels, but there were also objects of later periods, such as small stone bowls with coloured inlays which are best-known from the heavily looted Hellenistic Greek city-site of Ai Khanum in northern Afghanistan

(cf. Francfort 1979). Thanks to further scientific analyses, we were able to determine that ancient eye-liner in one 4,000-year-old container was white lead, to identify the species of wood inside the shaft-hole of a Bronze Age weapon and confirm its nineteenth/twentieth century BC date by radiocarbon dating, and that some puzzling miniature carved wooden heads were modern fakes, which we radiocarbon dated with a 91.7% probability that they date between 1988 and 1990: very similar pieces offered for sale more recently by an online auction house are likely to be of similar date (cf. Timeline Auctions 2015: lot 1393). Then UK Prime Minister David Cameron announced the return of the items during the course of an official visit to Kabul. This was followed by a formal hand-over ceremony at the British Museum, press releases in Dari and English simultaneously issued by the National Museum of Afghanistan and the British Museum, and a number of articles appeared in local and international media.

On 9th May 2016, we were fortunate in being able to return another important object to Kabul. This was an inscribed and dated Safavid tinned copper bowl which had been bought in good faith by an expatriate couple, Patrick and Paola von Aulock, living in Jeddah in 1994 (Fig. 6) (Forshaw 2016). The vendor of the object proved to be an Afghan antiques dealer, Mohammed Feda, and it now looks likely that other stolen or illegally exported Islamic items from Afghanistan were sold through the same route and may one day be successfully tracked down either in Saudi Arabia or some of its neighbouring countries, or from other expatriates who worked there at that time. The couple brought the bowl for evaluation at Christie's in London, where it was identified by Sara Plumbly, head of the Islamic Art Department at Christie's, as being a piece from the museum in Kabul as it had been published in 1974 by Melikian-Chirvani (1974: 552, 581, fig. 6), and later included as a comparison for one in the V&A Museum (Melikian-Chirvani 1982: 268–69, fig. 68). Christie's advised the owners that it was therefore impossible to sell at auction, and we entered into joint discussions about appropriate next steps: although understandably disappointed that they could not legally sell it, the couple very generously agreed instead to gift it to Afghanistan and we again acted as the third party (Fig. 7). We carefully timed this handover on 9th May 2016 to coincide with the arrival in London of President Ashraf Ghani and his predecessor, Hamid Karzai, and that very evening they were shown the bowl (Fig. 8). A few days later we received an email saying that the Director of the National Museum in Kabul had received the bowl, where it is now on display in their new Islamic Gallery.

In the meantime, on 4th March 2016, a small decorated silver flask was found among the personal possessions of an individual entering Gatwick Airport on a flight from

Denmark. It was declared by the importer to be modern and recently acquired in Dubai, but it was seized by a UK Border Force officer on suspicion of wrongful declaration and brought to the British Museum where it was confirmed to be ancient, looted from a site in Afghanistan and in breach of that country's Antiquities Law (Alberge 2018). Originally highlighted with gold overlays, the delicately engraved scenes on the flask represent two rows of humped bulls separated by plants with threefold pipal leaves (*Ficus religiosa*). It dates to the second half of the third millennium BC and was perhaps found in an ancient hoard, rather than a grave, as it was slightly deformed – most likely in antiquity – and missing most of the overlays (Fig. 9). The importer did not contest and the object became forfeit as Crown property and, in an official ceremony at the British Museum on 10th October 2018, was handed over by the museum's director, Dr Hartwig Fischer, to His Excellency Said Jawad, Ambassador of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, for return to the National Museum of Afghanistan (Fig. 10). There are few published scientific data on objects of precious metal of this period from that region, hence analysis of the composition was carried out in the Museum's Department of Scientific Research and included in a short article published soon after the repatriation (Simpson 2019).

The Afghan story does not end there. As early as September 2002, the Art and Antiques Unit of the Metropolitan Police Service had begun investigating another UK Border Force case, this time of a group of nine stunningly beautiful painted clay heads (Fig. 11), and a large carved schist sculpture (Fig. 12), which had been smuggled out of Afghanistan via Peshawar. In 2017 the objects were finally brought to the Museum for identification and confirmation of their provenance. The pieces obviously came from one or more Buddhist monasteries, and mostly represent male and female bodhisattvas who sought to achieve the enlightened status of Buddha. The women are depicted wearing elaborate diadems whereas the carver of the schist sculpture chose to highlight rich jewellery, in both cases underlining the high status of the individuals. Photographs were taken of the pieces and circulated to Buddhist specialists who confirmed the similarity of many of the heads to pieces known from monasteries in the Hadda area of Afghanistan, near Jalalabad and on a major ancient (and modern) route connecting Kabul to Peshawar (Thurston-Hoskins 2020), although the possibility that they came from the previously looted site of Mes Aynak, south of Kabul, cannot be discounted.

The Director of the National Museum in Kabul again agreed that we could scientifically analyse and display them before they were returned. Unfortunately, the objects were in very poor state as they had been badly packed and suffered in transit. Once more we are indebted to John Eskenazi for generously covering the considerable costs of their

conservation and mounting for display. Our own Department of Scientific Research also analysed the pigments used to colour the clay sculptures, and three were also CT-scanned so we have a record of how they were made (Fig. 13). We announced these pieces to the press at the launch of the British Museum *Annual Review*, where our Director, Dr Fischer, outlined the ways in which we work with other museums around the world (Brown 2019). At the invitation of the Ambassador of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, we also showed a selection of the pieces to the media at an event he organised to celebrate Afghan Media for Democracy, and they have been returned to Kabul through the Embassy.

Most trafficked objects on the market are from illegal excavations of archaeological sites, and therefore lack any provenance, and it is rare that we come across pieces we can prove come from a museum collection. However, in November 2019, a small high-relief limestone block representing humped bulls was offered for sale by the UK online sales platform as a ‘Western Asiatic Frieze Fragment with Bovines’ (Timeline 2019: lot 2170). This object was excavated at the important Kushan site of Surkh Kotal, and published not only in the excavation monograph but also in a catalogue of the objects in the National Museum in Kabul (Tissot 2006). It probably originally came from the inner part of the sanctuary of a temple which dates to the 2nd century AD, when this region of Afghanistan was part of the Kushan empire which stretched as far as northern India (Fig. 14). It was promptly reported by the Art Loss Register to the Metropolitan Police Service (Art and Antiques Unit) and disclaimed by its owner. Its provenance and stolen status were confirmed by the British Museum and the National Museum of Afghanistan who kindly agreed that this important sculpture be placed on public display prior to its return to Kabul (Alberge 2020a). It has now been packed for return to Kabul.

Uzbekistan

Thankfully, there is little evidence for looting of archaeological sites in Central Asia but the theft of glazed tiles from monuments, either during restoration or excavation in their vicinity, is evidently a problem as the next two cases illustrate.

On 18th July 2017, following a planned media announcement the previous day, a monumental glazed tile was handed over to Otabek Khojimatov, Cultural Attaché of the Islamic Republic of Uzbekistan, at a ceremony at the British Museum (Alberge 2017). This comes from an important Islamic monument known as the Chashma-i Ayub located in Vabkent, near Bukhara, in Uzbekistan. The building to which this tile belongs is a special eastern Islamic structure, which served as commemorative monuments and

consist of a tomb or memorial within an open enclosure with a monumental entrance. This is one of many in Central Asia that are dedicated to Job, a prophet in the Bible who was known in Islam as Ayyub. In Koranic tradition, Ayyub is regarded as a martyr and prophet who was rewarded with a source of water to soothe his skin afflictions, and in local Central Asian folklore he was viewed as a healer and a patron of silk farming, which was an important part of the economy of medieval Bukhara. The monument was constructed in the twelfth century, but later remodelled during a time when Bukhara was an important ‘Silk Road’ centre and the provincial capital of the powerful Karakhanid Empire. It was during this phase that a tall entrance was added with a magnificent high-relief turquoise glazed inscription along the top in *thuluth* script, a form of Islamic calligraphy (Fig. 15). This tile belongs to the end of this inscription, which reads: ‘The Prophet – peace be upon him – said: I had forbidden you to make pilgrimages to tombs. Now make pilgrimages. This monument was erected in the year five and six hundred’, which translates to AH 605, equivalent to AD 1208/1209 (Fig. 16). The inscription illustrates an important tension within Islam as to whether visiting the shrines of saints was a form of idolatry and forbidden in society. The construction of magnificent funerary monuments was a feature of Iran and Central Asia, and the combination of a colourful glazed turquoise tile section with relief brickwork is typical of these. This is one of the earliest surviving monuments in the region, and a particularly fine example of the architecture of the era.

This tile had been illegally removed from the building in about 2014 and offered for sale by the London dealer Simon Ray. Fortunately, Dr James Allan, former Keeper of Eastern Art at the Ashmolean Museum, who had visited the Chashma-i Ayub, recognized the tile when visiting the dealer’s website. He informed the gallery, and its owner immediately contacted us for advice and then brought the object to the Museum within hours. We then followed our normal process. The press release included statements by the Prime Minister of Uzbekistan, the Director of the British Museum, and the dealer, with the Uzbek Embassy arranging for the crate containing the tile to be returned (Fig. 17). The authorities in Uzbekistan conducted an official investigation and confirmed that the tile would be temporarily held by the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan in Tashkent until it is restored on the original monument itself as part of a high-profile public ceremony.

More recently, we have had a second case from the same country. On 24th January 2020, a passenger arriving at London Heathrow on an Emirates flight from Dubai caught the attention of a Border Force officer, and one of his suitcases found to contain six large epigraphic glazed tiles. He declared that they were replicas ‘made to look old’, were intended for sale and were accompanied by a receipt

describing them as ‘six decription [decoration] tiles’ purchased in Sharjah the previous day for 315 DH (the equivalent of about £70). They were detained on the grounds that their age required verification and later brought to the British Museum for verification once lockdown eased (Fig. 18). The tiles were clearly of a type found across Transoxiana: within days international experts contacted in America, Britain, Russia, Turkey and Central Asia excluded Iran, Afghanistan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan, and independently concurred that Uzbekistan had to be the country of origin. We contacted the Embassy in London and, through the Ministry of Culture, experts in Tashkent and Samarkand were invited to comment on the photographs. They agreed that the closest stylistic parallels for some were with monuments of the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries in the Shah-i Zinda complex next to Samarkand, although not from any of the standing monuments, suggesting that they may come from recent excavations. The story was then released to the media (Brown 2020), and a follow-up investigation with further recommendations will be actively pursued in 2021 once the pandemic allows.

Iraq

The effectiveness of the process we have been using, and outlined above, has been noted in other countries and serves as a textbook model for others to follow. One of these is Iraq. This is a country which has seen intermittent bouts of heavy looting of archaeological sites in the Diyala region and some of the southern provinces during the late nineteenth century, 1920s, 1990s and 2003/04 (Fig. 19). These were exceptional periods of weakened central authority and economic hardship. In contrast, the long intervening periods have been marked by greater stability, and employment of local villagers on archaeological projects has offered an alternative and welcomed source of income. Establishing to which period of such activity pieces on the art market belong is an area which requires expert knowledge as not all come from the recent looting, some pre-date the Antiquities Law of 1924, and others are recently trafficked but are accompanied by forged paperwork.

During the 1990s, there was limited success in proving the provenance of many pieces which flooded the market. Despite frequent claims in the media, there is very little evidence for pieces circulating which can be demonstrated to come from the period of Daesh control of regions in either northern Iraq – where there has been very little historic evidence of looting of sites – or Syria, and there is a depressing correlation with their propaganda statements and recorded acts of defacement and destruction which suggests the Daesh approach was predominantly iconoclastic rather than commercially driven (Simpson 2015*b*). The fate of the collection in Mosul museum is unclear: displayed statues

were shown being smashed but was the rest looted? None of the pieces have yet been identified on the market.

That said, we can highlight several cases of Mesopotamian antiquities which come from looting in southern Iraq in 2003. One was a small group seized on a Metropolitan Police warrant of a commercial premises in Mayfair on 2nd May that year. The dealer failed to supply proof of ownership, ceased trading and title passed to the Crown. After a long delay, the objects were eventually brought to the British Museum in 2018 where they were immediately identified as coming from Iraq, and more specifically originating from the site of Tello (Weiss 2019). They consisted of five Sumerian inscribed objects, two Jemdet Nasr stamp-seal amulets in the form of a reclining bull or showing a pair of quadrupeds facing in opposite directions, and an Achaemenid or post-Achaemenid stamp-seal showing a reclining sphinx (Fig. 20). The inscribed objects included three fired clay wall-cones with Sumerian inscriptions which identify their origin as the Eninnu temple at ancient Girsu (Fig. 21). This temple was sacred to the god’s patron deity, Ningirsu, and is located in the area of Tello known to modern scholarship as Tell A. This area has been a focus of recent UK Government-funded excavations carried out as part of the Iraq Emergency Heritage Management Training Scheme, not only revealing the plan and extent of this important complex but also many inscribed wall cones still *in situ* in the temple walls (Fig. 22). This not only demonstrates the exact spot where they had been looted in April 2003, but proved that they had been moved very quickly onto the market as they were seized in London within a month. The other items are also identical to objects known from excavations at Tello, and most likely originate from the same site.

Tello was first explored archaeologically in 1877 by a French team directed by Ernest de Sarzec (1832–1901), and these investigations continued for a total of twenty seasons until 1933. Following that, the site remained untouched until looting began at the beginning of 2003 according to information from the State Board of Antiquities and Heritage authorities (Nasiriyah), Thi Qar archaeological police and local tribesmen. This scene of crime was recorded in 2015 as part of an initial survey of the site (Rey 2016), and in more detail in 2017, and shown to consist of dozens of pits measuring two to three metres across and demonstrated by excavations in Tell A to reach a depth of up to two metres below the present surface, but no deeper than the level of the *in situ* cones (Fig. 23). These pits are concentrated in certain areas of the site: the largest number are on the western side of Tell A, followed by the Sacred City between Tell A and Tell K, and Tell V, also known as ‘Mound of the Tablets’, and where most of the cuneiform objects looted between 1909 and 1929 had been found. This activity was clandestine and probably carried out at night as two broken bottles reused as

lamps were recovered from within a looting hole excavated in 2018 (Fig. 24). This illicit activity corresponds to a phase of widespread looting of particular archaeological sites in southern Iraq between the 1990s and 2004, and complete inscribed cones of Gudea continued to be offered for sale during this period.

On 10th August 2018 a small official ceremony was held at the British Museum to mark the official handover of this group of objects. Those present included Dr Salih Husain Ali, then the Ambassador of the Republic of Iraq to the UK, Dr Hartwig Fischer, Director of the British Museum, and staff and representatives of the Embassy of the Republic of Iraq, the British Museum, the Metropolitan Police and the British Government's Department of Culture, Media and Sport. The objects were presented to Dr Husain Ali by Dr Fischer, official paperwork signed and exchanged (Fig. 25), photographs taken and the objects taken to the Embassy of the Republic of Iraq, where a press event was organised which included mass media from across the Arab world. The event attracted huge attention globally and shows how the world values and treasures the rich cultural heritage of Iraq (Fig. 26). Following official practice and the request of the State Board of Antiquities and Heritage in Baghdad, a short joint report was submitted for publication in its annual journal, *Sumer* (Simpson *et al.* in press a).

The other objects also came from looting in 2003. One was a Babylonian boundary stone, an object known as a *kudurru*, and dated by its inscription to the reign of Nebuchadnezzar I (r. circa 1126–1103 BC). He was the fourth king of the Second Dynasty of Isin, was the most prominent monarch of his dynasty and won a great victory over Elam when he recovered the statue of the Babylonian state god, Marduk (Fig. 27). This boundary stone was imported via the United Arab Emirates, seized at Heathrow airport by UK Border Force in 2012 and authenticity and age confirmed at the British Museum. The case was investigated in detail by Her Majesty's Revenue and Customs, and the object declared Crown Property when the exporter failed to demonstrate legal title. It was handed over by the Director of the British Museum, Dr Hartwig Fischer, to Dr Salih Husain Ali Altamimi, Ambassador of the Republic of Iraq as representative of the Government of Iraq, in a small ceremony at the British Museum on 19th March 2019, and immediately sent to Baghdad where it was transferred from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to the Iraq Museum and a short report again submitted to *Sumer* (Simpson *et al.* in press b).

A third case was of 156 clay tablets written in cuneiform script (Fig. 28). These range in date from the mid-third millennium BC to the Achaemenid period (sixth-fourth centuries BC). The earliest are Sumerian Early Dynastic/

Sargonic administrative tablets, some are blackened by fire. The latest date to the reigns of the Achaemenid rulers Darius I (522–486 BC) and Artaxerxes I (465–425 BC) or II (404–359 BC). There is also a single tablet of the little-known late Babylonian king Nabonassar (747–734 BC), who became a vassal of the Assyrian ruler Tiglath-Pileser III (745–727 BC). However, most date to the period between 2100 and 1800 BC, and belong to the Ur III and Old Babylonian dynasties. Some of the third millennium BC tablets may be from Umma and some Old Babylonian texts come from Larsa, but many belong to administrative archives coming from a place called Irisagrig. During the Ur III period this was a provincial city of sufficient cultic and economic note, with a temple of Ninhursag, that rulers from Ur used to visit it regularly. The exact location of this was unclear until large numbers of tablets referring to Irisagrig surfaced on the art market in 2003. The sudden appearance of these indicate that the site – like many others in southern Iraq – must have been heavily looted that year and all texts from Irisagrig must have been illegally trafficked in breach of the antiquities law of Iraq. Some of these tablets were confiscated by Jordanian authorities in 2003/2004 and returned to Iraq (Menegazzi 2005: 79) and others began to be studied in 2004 (Owen 2013: vol. 1, 28–31). Among the information given on the texts themselves is that it took four days to tow a boat upstream from Umma. Some scholars initially located the site in the proximity of Nippur, and Steinkeller (2001) and Molina (2013) suggested either Adams site 1032 or site 1056, both on a palaeo-channel of the Tigris. However, Viano (2019) has instead proposed an identification with the 64 hectare (looted) site of Tell al-Wilayah as that is located on a major ancient water-channel and is much larger than the other sites; Irisagrig is known to have been located near the ancient city of Keš, and Keš has now been identified as the nearby site of Tulul al-Baqarat on the basis of inscriptions found there. Moreover, the distance of 75 km from Umma to Tell Wilaya is consistent with an estimated daily towing pace of 15–20 km a day for an empty boat. A careful examination of the looted spoil should quickly determine which is correct as it is clear from our experience at Tello that looters discard broken objects, whether inscribed or not, as they are acting on instructions that only complete objects are saleable and these are usually moved to market as quickly as possible.

This group of tablets therefore comes from a small number of archaeological sites in this region of Babylonia where we know there was heavy looting in 2003 (Stone 2008). This is the largest group of cuneiform tablets to be seized in the UK and returned to Iraq. They were incorrectly declared as 'miniature clay tiles' on entry to the UK from Sharjah (United Arab Emirates) in February 2011. After a detailed investigation by the UK's Fraud Investigation Service of HMRC, they were seized from the freight forwarder near Heathrow Airport, identified, catalogued

and photographed at the British Museum, handed over in a second ceremony at the British Museum on 29th August 2019, and are now also safely in the Iraq Museum (Simpson *et al.* in press *b*). It might be added that other tablets from the site of Irisagrig have been returned recently to Iraq by the American federal authorities following investigation of the Hobby Lobby group (Arraf 2018): rather tellingly, these too had also been imported from the United Arab Emirates and described as ‘miniature clay tiles’. Wherever else such objects are identified, it is clear that they must have been looted and illegally exported, making them an equally clear-cut case for investigation and repatriation (cf. Brodie 2011).

In May 2019 another looted antiquity was identified for sale by Timeline Auctions, where it was misleadingly described as a ‘Western Asiatic Akkadian tablet’, and said to come from a private collection formed in the 1990s but without any further provenance. It was reported by the British Museum to the Metropolitan Police Service (Art and Antiques Unit) who, following further enquiries, brought the plaque for examination at the Museum as the consigner swiftly disclaimed ownership (Alberge 2020*b*). This finely carved limestone fragment dates from about 2400 BC and shows a seated male, either a high-priest or a ruler, holding a goblet (Fig. 29). It is part of a larger square wall-plaque which would have shown a ritual banquet scene. Plaques in this particular style are only known from temples in important Sumerian city-sites in present-day southern Iraq, and it most likely comes from looting of a site there between the 1990s and 2003. On 22nd October 2020 it was installed on display with the permission of the Minister of Culture, Hassan Nadhem, and shown the following day to Mustafa al-Kadhimi, Prime Minister of the Republic of Iraq, when he made a special visit to the British Museum at the end of an official government visit to the UK, France and Germany (Al-Monitor 2020). It will be repatriated to Iraq with the generous assistance of His Excellency, Mohammad Jafer al-Sadr, Ambassador of the Republic of Iraq in London.

Conclusions

These successive cases from Afghanistan, Uzbekistan and Iraq demonstrate the effectiveness and impact of the close working relationship and trust developed between the British Museum, the national museums and Ministries of Culture in host countries, and different branches of UK and international law enforcement, and the trade. In many cases, we have also briefly exhibited some of these objects, either as part of the special exhibition *Afghanistan: Crossroads of the Ancient World* (2011), or as rotating displays in a special showcase designed to illustrate our role in helping fight illicit trafficking, and share these objects for public benefit prior to repatriation. These displays are endorsed by our counterparts abroad and their Embassies in London, and the

regular handover and steady repatriation of these trafficked antiquities is again closely co-ordinated with and agreed by all parties. In some cases, the number and/or value of the objects are not inconsiderable and their seizure financially hurt the dealers and remove the items from the market. However, there is a symbolic value too: the return of any objects, regardless of value, age or size, sends a strong message of solidarity. Antiquities trafficking is a global phenomenon and requires equivalent networks to combat it effectively: ours is one such network which has demonstrable impact and actions beyond words. We strongly believe that these examples, and the processes we adhere to, serve as a robust model for future cases involving other countries.

Figures

Fig. 1. Antiquities return to Kabul on a military flight thanks to the assistance of the British Armed Forces (photograph: Crown / Ministry of Defence, 2012)

Fig. 3. Begram ivories on temporary display as part of the British Museum special exhibition, *Afghanistan: Crossroads of the Ancient World* (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 2. Unpacking newly conserved Begram ivories at the British Museum in March 2011. Stolen from the National Museum in Kabul during the civil war (1992–1994), these were acquired and conserved on their behalf by a private benefactor: this photograph captures the moment when museum staff and members of the Institute of Archaeology (Academy of Sciences) in Kabul saw them for the first time since their theft over twenty years previously (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 4. The 'Fire Buddha' goes back on display in Kabul with Dr Masoudi and the late Nancy Hatch Dupree (photograph: Andy Miller)

Fig. 5. 4,000-year-old cosmetic flask from a looted Bronze Age cemetery in northern Afghanistan (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 8. The bowl is shown to President Ashraf Ghani at the Embassy of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan in London: it is now on display in the National Museum in Kabul (photograph: Embassy of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan)

Fig. 6. Safavid tinned copper wine bowl stolen from the National Museum of Afghanistan, and acquired and presented by Mr and Mrs von Aulock (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 9. Drawing of a decorated silver flask with remains of gold overlay (drawing by the author, digitised by Kate Morton)

Fig. 7. Official handover ceremony for the Safavid bowl at the British Museum with Mrs von Aulock, Sara Plumbly (Christie's) and officials from the Embassy of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 10. The silver flask is shown to His Excellency Said Jawad, ambassador of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 11. Buddhist heads seized by the Metropolitan Police (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 14. Surkh Kotal bull (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 12. Gandharan sculpture seized by the UK Border Force in 2002 and investigated by the Art and Antiques Unit of the Metropolitan Police Service (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 15. The Chashma-i Ayub monument with the missing tile at top left (photograph: Prof. J. Allan)

Fig. 13. CT-scan made in the Department of Scientific Research at the British Museum, showing how one of the Buddhist heads was built up with fine stucco on top of a coarse core (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 16. Stolen Islamic tile from the Chashma-i Ayub being shown at an official handover ceremony at the British Museum (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 17. The glazed tile is packed and ready for return to Tashkent (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 20. Fired clay cones and other antiquities looted from Tello (ancient Girsu) in their presentation box prior to repatriation (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 18. Glazed tile from Uzbekistan (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 21. Fired clay wall cone looted from the Eninnu temple at Tello (Girsu) prior to repatriation

Fig. 19. View across a heavily looted early second millennium BC site in the Nasiriyah region of southern Iraq (photograph: author, 2018)

Fig. 22. Excavating inscribed cones from the walls of the temple (Tello-Girsu Project, Iraq Scheme, The British Museum)

Fig. 23. Dr Sebastien Rey surveying looting pits with armed forces of the SBAH archaeological police unit in 2015 (photograph: Tello-Girsu Project, Iraq Scheme, The British Museum)

Fig. 26. Addressing the media at the Republic of Iraq Embassy (photograph: Embassy of the Republic of Iraq)

Fig. 24. Modern bottle reused as a night lamp and other items found in a modern looting hole at Tello during excavations in 2018 (Tello-Girsu Project, Iraq Scheme, The British Museum)

Fig. 27. Babylonian *kudurru* seized by UK Border Force (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 25. Official handover ceremony with exchange of paperwork by His Excellency Dr Husain Ali, Ambassador to the Republic of Iraq, and Dr Fischer, Director of the British Museum (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 28. Cuneiform tablets investigated by Her Majesty's Revenue and Customs prior to repatriation (photograph: The British Museum)

Fig. 29. Sumerian plaque press (photograph: The British Museum)

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Letter from the Editor

What a bizarre year. It can only get better, right? The world has been on pause then shifted to virtual: from work to education, online options seem to be the way forward. Our Academic Program, which is the focus of our educational offerings, and our annual conference, are both paused until travel and convening are safe and advisable, which means that 2020 and 2021 are both washes. We will shift some material to virtual and online options, but mostly we'll look forward to resuming what has been a beloved and successful on-site tradition every summer, a touchstone that so many look forward to.

ARCA Publications continues to grow. In addition to *Transnational Art Crime* by Edgar Tjihuis, *The Art Thief's Handbook* by Noah Charney and *Context Matters* by David Gill, already available on Amazon, we will shortly release *The Caravaggio Diaries* by Father Marius Zerafa and *The Secret Collector* by Leon Pogelšek and Slavko Pregl, which is excerpted in this issue.

While our normal, on-site offerings are paused we have begun to do more media-outreach projects, and at a noteworthy scale. Just this November two big ones came out. Lynda Albertson, our CEO, featured in *Lot 448*, an art crime documentary film that premiered on Amazon Prime, and she and I are fronting a large-scale campaign for Samsung called "Missing Masterpieces" in which we curated a collection of lost paintings that can be viewed online, where crowdsourced tips can suggest their locations, and on Samsung The Frame TV sets. More such media projects will follow. As always, thank you for your support and happy reading!

Noah Charney
Founder, ARCA
Co-Editor-in-Chief, *The Journal of Art Crime*